

Multi-omics gut microbiome signatures in obese women: role of diet and uncontrolled eating behavior

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Supplementary Material

Figure S1. Assignment of bacterial co-abundance groups (CAGs). CAGs were assigned according to the heat plot (a) showing Kendall correlations between genera clustered by the Spearman correlation coefficient and Ward linkage hierarchical clustering. (b) Wiggum plot correlation between the five CAGs identified. Circle size is proportional to the genus relative abundance and the connections between nodes represent significant correlations between genera (Kendall, FDR < 0.05). Positive correlations are represented by continuous lines, while negative correlations are represented by dashed lines. Thickness of the lines is proportional to the significance of the correlation.

Figure S2. Associations of the microbiota profiles with host metadata. Unweighted UniFrac PCoA of the fecal microbiota in the whole cohort (a), as well as in normal-weight women (NW, b) and overweight/obese women (OB, c), stratified according to the four microbiota clusters (C1-C4, see Fig. 3). The host variables significantly associated with the axes are highlighted. MDS, multidimensional scaling.

Figure S3. Distribution of eating behavior-based study groups across the four microbiome clusters (C1-C4). Women were stratified based on addictive eating behavior into 4 groups: NW_NA (normal-weight, non-addicted), O_LA (overweight/obese, low-addicted), O_HA (overweight/obese, high-addicted), and O_DHA (overweight/obese, high-addicted with food addiction diagnosis). See Methods for further details on stratification.

Figure S4. The transcriptionally active fraction of the gut microbiome differs according to obesity and uncontrolled eating behavior. (a) Bubble charts showing the transcriptionally active microbial species within the four microbiome configurations (clusters C1-C4). Circle sizes and colors indicate the transcriptional over-abundance of a given species compared to its average normalized abundance in the whole cohort using log₂ transformation. (b) Spider plots showing the number of active species for each metabolism (i.e., carbohydrate, lipid, amino acid and xenobiotic metabolism). Species were counted as “active” when present with log₂ normalized abundance > 1 in at least 1/3 of the pathways comprised in the specific metabolic category.

Figure S6. Metabolic activities of the four microbiota clusters according to metatranscriptomic analysis. Expression levels of the 57 identified KEGG pathways related to amino acid (red), carbohydrate (blue), lipid (green), and xenobiotic (grey) metabolisms that were most prevalently transcribed among the species detected by metagenomics, for the microbiome clusters C1 (a), C2 (b), C3 (c) and C4 (d).

Figure S7. Fecal lipidomic profiles of the four microbiota clusters (C1-C4). Boxplots showing the amount distribution of short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs, upper panel), sterols (middle panel) and bile acids (lower panel) significantly different between the four microbiota clusters. CA, cholic acid; CDCA, chenodeoxycholic acid; GDCA, glycocholic acid; Glyco, glycoconjugates. See [50] for further details on fecal lipidomics analysis. *, $p \leq 0.05$; **, $p \leq 0.01$; ***, $p \leq 0.001$; Wilcoxon test.

Figure S8. Associations between the transcriptionally active fraction of the gut microbiome and lipidomics measures. Hierarchical clustering obtained with complete linkage as distance, performed on the sparse partial least square (sPLS) regression of transcriptionally active pathways and species of the gut microbiome and host lipids. CA, cholic acid; CDCA, chenodeoxycholic acid; DCA, deoxycholic acid; GCA, glycocholic acid; GDCA, glycodeoxycholic acid; HDCA, hyodeoxycholic acid; LCA, lithocholic acid; UDCA, ursodeoxycholic acid.

Figure S9. Transcriptional activities of microbiome configurations specifically related to food intake, energy expenditure and neuroendocrine signaling. Average RNA:DNA ratio for each cluster (C1-C4) with respect to the whole cohort, of a selection of key genes involved in ClpB (orange), bile acid (brown), tryptophan (green), opioid (cyan), eCB (violet), and GABA (navy) production, divided by the assigned microbial species. Phylogenetic tree on the top of the heatmap was built using hierarchical Ward linkage clustering based on the Spearman correlation coefficients of the average DNA-normalized transcript abundance profiles for the species with detectable transcriptomes in the whole cohort.

Table S1. Genus-level distribution and differences in the gut microbiota profiles among the four clusters (C1-C4). For each genus, the mean relative abundance and sem (standard error of the mean) are reported, along with Wilcoxon test *p* values (significant values in bold).

Genus	relative abundances								p values					
	mean C1	sem C1	mean C2	sem C2	mean C3	sem C3	mean C4	sem C4	C1 vs C2	C1 vs C3	C1 vs C4	C2 vs C3	C2 vs C4	C3 vs C4
<i>Anaerotruncus</i>	0.0038	0.0013	0.0049	0.0017	0.03	0.0077	0.019	0.0094	0.8	0.00004	0.07	0.0001	0.1	0.1
<i>Coprobacillus</i>	0.023	0.0094	0.032	0.013	0.048	0.021	0.2	0.11	0.7	0.6	0.03	0.4	0.02	0.2
<i>Eggerthella</i>	0.026	0.011	0.32	0.081	0.054	0.034	0.13	0.048	8.00E-06	0.3	0.002	0.0006	0.3	0.03
<i>Butyricimonas</i>	0.034	0.0076	0.062	0.03	0.14	0.056	0.0054	0.0027	0.08	0.03	0.02	0.002	0.5	0.0009
<i>Lachnobacterium</i>	0.035	0.017	0.013	0.0061	0.081	0.058	0.0046	0.0027	0.03	0.8	0.05	0.03	0.7	0.05
[<i>Prevotella</i>]	0.057	0.049	0	0	0.13	0.11	0	0	0.07	0.2	0.2	0.005	NA	0.06
<i>Slackia</i>	0.059	0.019	0.042	0.021	0.18	0.093	0.16	0.11	0.1	0.1	0.4	0.007	0.7	0.09
<i>Desulfovibrio</i>	0.061	0.034	0.022	0.016	0.2	0.081	0.0062	0.0054	0.4	0.1	0.3	0.03	0.7	0.06
<i>Veillonella</i>	0.094	0.026	0.3	0.2	0.01	0.0033	0.024	0.014	0.5	0.0004	0.009	0.004	0.05	0.7
<i>Adlercreutzia</i>	0.19	0.057	0.074	0.028	0.13	0.033	0.29	0.063	0.0002	0.5	0.04	0.005	0.0001	0.02
<i>Turicibacter</i>	0.21	0.1	0.16	0.073	0.091	0.026	0.28	0.095	0.02	0.5	0.3	0.2	0.04	0.08
<i>Catenibacterium</i>	0.26	0.17	0.13	0.13	0.5	0.29	0	0	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.01	0.3	0.01
<i>Anaerostipes</i>	0.3	0.042	0.19	0.043	0.23	0.057	0.24	0.082	0.02	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.7
<i>Parabacteroides</i>	0.4	0.064	0.6	0.17	0.42	0.066	0.079	0.035	0.2	0.7	0.0001	0.1	0.07	0.00004
<i>Phascolarctobacterium</i>	0.48	0.1	0.25	0.12	1.06	0.27	0.33	0.22	0.01	0.2	0.05	0.002	0.8	0.01
<i>Roseburia</i>	0.62	0.11	0.46	0.099	0.21	0.049	0.24	0.061	0.1	0.001	0.02	0.4	0.8	0.4
<i>Clostridium</i>	0.67	0.077	0.83	0.14	0.37	0.09	0.25	0.074	0.6	0.006	0.002	0.04	0.02	0.4
[<i>Ruminococcus</i>]	0.99	0.14	2.94	0.59	0.84	0.16	1.37	0.25	0.001	0.4	0.1	0.0008	0.1	0.04
<i>Akkermansia</i>	1.5	0.31	0.39	0.21	6.74	1.71	4.9	1.88	0.00009	0.03	0.9	0.00006	0.05	0.3
<i>Lachnospira</i>	1.54	0.36	1.48	0.41	1.13	0.22	0.32	0.14	0.3	0.8	0.0004	0.4	0.04	0.002
<i>Collinsella</i>	1.73	0.21	2.02	0.42	1.95	0.33	4.92	0.91	0.4	0.8	0.001	0.5	0.003	0.005
<i>Coprococcus</i>	1.75	0.3	0.33	0.074	2.38	0.5	0.94	0.31	3.00E-07	0.4	0.03	2.00E-06	0.03	0.02
<i>Prevotella</i>	2.23	0.72	0.18	0.12	1.89	0.7	0.083	0.034	0.002	0.6	0.08	0.0002	0.3	0.02
<i>Bifidobacterium</i>	5.55	0.9	11.14	1.38	4.59	1.05	17.84	3.51	0.001	0.4	0.0002	0.00008	0.05	0.0002
<i>Ruminococcus</i>	5.87	0.46	2.45	0.71	5.36	0.91	6.47	1.11	1.00E-06	0.1	0.7	0.00009	0.001	0.3
<i>Blautia</i>	7.33	0.81	10.68	1.51	3.86	0.61	8.39	1.32	0.1	0.001	0.6	0.00007	0.5	0.003
<i>Bacteroides</i>	8.44	0.98	9.07	1.62	7.68	1.82	2.84	1	0.5	0.2	0.0004	0.9	0.09	0.02
<i>Faecalibacterium</i>	10.43	0.83	7.61	1.03	5.99	0.97	3.05	0.75	0.05	0.0004	6.00E-07	0.5	0.03	0.04

Table S2. Food description and average frequency of daily consumption for each microbiota cluster (C1 to C4).

Food	Description	Food category	Microbiota group			
			C1	C2	C3	C4
bisquits and sweet snacks	Biscuits, packaged cakes or pastries	Snacks	0.385	0.417	0.215	0.567
cheese	Grated, sliced or spreadable cheese	Cheese	0.25	0.312	0.288	0.333
chocolate	Chocolate candy and bars	Snacks	0.244	0.231	0.182	0.183
eggs	Boiled or fried eggs	Eggs	0.11	0.099	0.092	0.088
fried food	Fried food	Other	0.111	0.077	0.082	0.11
fried potatoes	Fried potatoes	Vegetable	0.084	0.099	0.067	0.076
homemade sandwiches	Hamburger, hotdog, kebab, wrap, falafel	Cereal	0.198	0.149	0.206	0.152
ice cream	Ice cream, milk and fruit based bars	Snacks	0.138	0.135	0.123	0.062
meat	Fresh and fried meat	Meat Products	0.088	0.117	0.086	0.138
milk and yoghurt	Milk and plain sweetened yoghurt	Dairy Products	0.481	0.664	0.464	0.683
not homemade sandwiches	Hamburger, hotdog, kebab, wrap, falafel	Cereal	0.076	0.064	0.092	0.112
olive oil	Vegetable dressing	Fat and oils	0.658	0.784	0.561	0.776
pizza	Pizza	Cereal	0.146	0.14	0.185	0.133
sausages	Cold cuts and preserved meat product	Meat Products	0.038	0.072	0.029	0.043
seasonings and condiments	Butter, margarine on bread, pesto, ragù	Condiments	0.214	0.244	0.089	0.217
slide ham	Cold cuts and preserved meat product	Meat Products	0.116	0.139	0.12	0.167
sweet and salty snacks	Packaged cakes or savoury pastries and fritters	Snacks	0.204	0.244	0.155	0.16
sweetened drinks	Sweetened soft beverages	Drinks	0.118	0.195	0.092	0.1
wine	Alcoholic beverages	Drinks	0.189	0.172	0.273	0.16

Table S3. Summary of dietary groups and microbiota clusters for each of the 100 enrolled women. Women were stratified based on addictive eating behavior into 4 groups: NW_NA (normal-weight, non-addicted), O_LA (overweight/obese, low-addicted), O_HA (overweight/obese, high-addicted), and O_DHA (overweight/obese, high-addicted with food addiction diagnosis). For microbiota clusters and dietary groups, see Fig. 3 and Fig. 5, respectively.

SampleID	Group	Microbiota cluster	Diet group
NEU10B	O_LA	C3	D1
NEU116B	O_HA	C2	D3
NEU117B	O_NA	C4	D3
NEU118B	O_NA	C2	D1
NEU119B	O_LA	C2	D1
NEU11B	O_NA	C4	D1
NEU127B	O_LA	C4	D3
NEU129B	O_NA	C2	D2
NEU12B	O_LA	C2	D1
NEU134B	O_HA	C3	D2
NEU139B	O_NA	C1	D3
NEU13B	O_LA	C1	D3
NEU144B	O_NA	C3	D2
NEU14B	O_LA	C4	D1
NEU152B	O_NA	C1	D1
NEU153B	O_LA	C4	D1
NEU155B	O_LA	C3	D3
NEU160B	O_NA	C2	D1
NEU161B	O_LA	C1	D1
NEU163B	O_LA	C4	D1
NEU164B	O_LA	C2	D3
NEU167B	O_NA	C3	D2
NEU16B	O_HA	C2	D1
NEU170B	O_NA	C1	D2
NEU172B	O_NA	C2	D1
NEU174B	O_HA	C2	D2
NEU176B	O_NA	C1	D2
NEU177B	O_LA	C3	D3
NEU178B	O_HA	C3	D1
NEU179B	O_LA	C1	D1
NEU17B	O_HA	C2	D1
NEU180B	O_LA	C1	D2
NEU18B	O_HA	C1	D1
NEU19B	O_HA	C3	D1
NEU1B	O_NA	C3	D3
NEU20B	O_HA	C3	D3
NEU21B	O_HA	C4	D1
NEU22B	O_HA	C2	D1
NEU23B	O_HA	C2	D1
NEU25B	O_NA	C1	D1
NEU26B	O_NA	C1	D1
NEU27B	O_LA	C3	D3
NEU28B	O_NA	C1	D3
NEU29B	O_NA	C2	D1
NEU2B	O_NA	C2	D1
NEU30B	O_NA	C1	D1
NEU31B	O_LA	C1	D3
NEU32B	O_HA	C3	D2
NEU33B	O_HA	C3	D3
NEU34B	O_NA	C2	D3
NEU35B	O_LA	C2	D3
NEU36B	O_NA	C2	D2
NEU37B	O_NA	C2	D1
NEU38B	O_NA	C2	D1
NEU39B	O_LA	C2	D3
NEU3B	O_LA	C1	D3
NEU4B	O_LA	C4	D1
NEU5B	O_NA	C2	D1
NEU6B	O_NA	C2	D1
NEU7B	O_NA	C3	D3
NEU8B	O_HA	C1	D1
NEU9B	O_LA	C2	D1

SampleID	Group	Microbiota cluster	Diet group
NC120B	NW_NA	C1	D1
NC121B	NW_NA	C2	D2
NC122B	NW_NA	C1	D3
NC123B	NW_NA	C1	D3
NC124B	NW_NA	C2	D3
NC125B	NW_NA	C2	D3
NC126B	NW_NA	C1	D1
NC128B	NW_NA	C2	D1
NC130B	NW_NA	C2	D1
NC131B	NW_NA	C1	D1
NC132B	NW_NA	C1	D3
NC133B	NW_NA	C3	D3
NC135B	NW_NA	C2	D1
NC136B	NW_NA	C1	D1
NC137B	NW_NA	C4	D2
NC138B	NW_NA	C4	D1
NC140B	NW_NA	C1	D3
NC141B	NW_NA	C3	D2
NC142B	NW_NA	C1	D2
NC143B	NW_NA	C4	D2
NC145B	NW_NA	C1	D2
NC146B	NW_NA	C3	D3
NC147B	NW_NA	C1	D1
NC148B	NW_NA	C2	D2
NC149B	NW_NA	C4	D1
NC150B	NW_NA	C3	D1
NC151B	NW_NA	C1	D2
NC154B	NW_NA	C4	D1
NC156B	O_HA	C4	D3
NC157B	NW_NA	C3	D1
NC159B	NW_NA	C1	D2
NC162B	NW_NA	C3	D1
NC165B	NW_NA	C2	D2
NC166B	NW_NA	C1	D1
NC168B	NW_NA	C3	D2
NC171B	NW_NA	C1	D1
NC173B	NW_NA	C3	D2
NC175B	NW_NA	C2	D1

Table S4. Loading scores obtained from sPLS correlation analysis between metatranscriptomics and lipidomics datasets. UDCA, ursodeoxycholic acid; HDCA, hyodeoxycholic acid; GCA, glycocholic acid; CA, cholic acid; CDCA, chenodeoxycholic acid; GDCA, glycodeoxycholic acid; DCA, deoxycholic acid; LCA, lithocholic acid; Free, free bile acids; Glyco, glycine-conjugated bile acids; Primary, primary bile acids; Secondary, secondary bile acids; Total, total bile acids. See also Fig. 9.

	comp1	comp2		comp1	comp2
Alanine_aspartate_glutamate_metabolism <i>Bacteroides uniformis</i>	0.009235	0.04616256	Glyoxylate_dicarboxylate_metabolism <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	-0.0018626	-0.0259434
Alanine_aspartate_glutamate_metabolism <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	-0.0520611	-0.0977455	Glyoxylate_dicarboxylate_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	0.15205624	-0.0005026
Alanine_aspartate_glutamate_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	0.0855606	0.0572781	Glyoxylate_dicarboxylate_metabolism <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	0.03103988	-0.060727
Alanine_aspartate_glutamate_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	0.15288117	0.01184153	Histidine_metabolism <i>Bacteroides uniformis</i>	-0.0371093	-0.0523
Alanine_aspartate_glutamate_metabolism <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	-0.0137712	-0.0794428	Histidine_metabolism <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	-0.0304953	-0.0840892
Alanine_aspartate_glutamate_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	0.14664802	0.05194782	Histidine_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	-0.0312191	-0.048457
Alanine_aspartate_glutamate_metabolism <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	-0.0391005	-0.0701839	Histidine_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	-0.0598143	-0.1302051
Aminosugar_nucleotidesugar_metabolism <i>Bacteroides uniformis</i>	-0.0166901	-0.0101881	Histidine_metabolism <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	-0.0504765	-0.0841557
Aminosugar_nucleotidesugar_metabolism <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	-0.0359378	-0.0556378	Histidine_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	-0.0202314	0.0205642
Aminosugar_nucleotidesugar_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	0.03401977	0.06051082	Histidine_metabolism <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	0.0425901	-0.0804564
Aminosugar_nucleotidesugar_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	0.16476177	-0.0168718	Inositol_phosphate_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	-0.0183562	-0.109768
Aminosugar_nucleotidesugar_metabolism <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	-0.0095053	-0.1217103	Lysine_biosynthesis <i>Bacteroides uniformis</i>	-0.048137	-0.1029858
Aminosugar_nucleotidesugar_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	0.02032995	0.04422082	Lysine_biosynthesis <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	0.00215933	0.01680654
Aminosugar_nucleotidesugar_metabolism <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	-0.0430462	-0.06318	Lysine_biosynthesis <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	-0.0760526	-0.1552683
Arginine_biosynthesis <i>Bacteroides uniformis</i>	0.17587216	0.134575	Lysine_biosynthesis <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	0.02126343	-0.0921346
Arginine_biosynthesis <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	-0.04415	0.0850094	Lysine_biosynthesis <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	0.13341229	-0.1173083
Arginine_biosynthesis <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	0.17454724	0.01654483	Lysine_biosynthesis <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	0.12420193	-0.0249484
Arginine_biosynthesis <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	0.17555578	0.00256697	Pentose_glucuronate_+E19	-0.0069456	-0.0172927
Arginine_biosynthesis <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	0.19039125	0.02537051	Pentose_glucuronate_interconversions <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	0.00663459	-0.0593316
Arginine_biosynthesis <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	0.15123445	-0.016064	Pentose_glucuronate_interconversions <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	-0.0051937	-0.0319584
Arginine_biosynthesis <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	-0.0451281	-0.1084412	Pentose_glucuronate_interconversions <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	0.20427309	0.06553809
Arginine_proline_metabolism <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	-0.0532033	-0.112923	Pentose_glucuronate_interconversions <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	0.14343727	0.05493857
Arginine_proline_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	0.10478334	0.22925757	Pentose_phosphate_pathway <i>Bacteroides uniformis</i>	0.00811933	0.04530702
Arginine_proline_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	-0.0367454	-0.0869794	Pentose_phosphate_pathway <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	-0.0045012	0.0111527
Arginine_proline_metabolism <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	0.1014597	-0.0562661	Pentose_phosphate_pathway <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	-0.0484244	-0.0878174
Arginine_proline_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	0.05237896	-0.0650532	Pentose_phosphate_pathway <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	0.12240484	-0.074938
Arginine_proline_metabolism <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	0.00157108	0.02449597	Pentose_phosphate_pathway <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	0.18759885	0.02499292
Benzoate_degradation <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	-0.0118867	-0.1170003	Pentose_phosphate_pathway <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	0.15597607	0.03684897
Benzoate_degradation <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	-0.0390719	0.0850094	Pentose_phosphate_pathway <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	0.0232488	-0.1131332
Butanoate_metabolism <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	0.0382804	0.0681517	Phenylalanine_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	-0.0540729	-0.1256542
Butanoate_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	-0.0028901	-0.0139872	Phenylalanine_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	-0.0271171	-0.1023913
Butanoate_metabolism <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	0.03207697	-0.0690874	Phenylalanine_tyrosine_tryptophan_biosynthesis <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	-0.0619938	-0.1662977
Butanoate_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	-0.0369	-0.0113378	Phenylalanine_tyrosine_tryptophan_biosynthesis <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	-0.0503946	-0.101115
Butanoate_metabolism <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	-0.0273715	-0.0793332	Phenylalanine_tyrosine_tryptophan_biosynthesis <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	-0.0264788	-0.0627147
C5-branched_dibasic_acid_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	0.0445968	-0.0990282	Phenylalanine_tyrosine_tryptophan_biosynthesis <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	-0.045295	-0.0911387
C5-branched_dibasic_acid_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	-0.1668302	0.02599513	Phenylalanine_tyrosine_tryptophan_biosynthesis <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	-0.0767918	-0.1693123
C5-branched_dibasic_acid_metabolism <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	0.02757989	-0.0595254	Phenylalanine_tyrosine_tryptophan_biosynthesis <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	-0.0358508	-0.053102
C5-branched_dibasic_acid_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	-0.0048205	0.00776443	Propanoate_metabolism <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	-0.0292632	-0.0406072
C5-branched_dibasic_acid_metabolism <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	-0.0268406	-0.0795628	Propanoate_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	0.09747076	-0.0349509
Gltate_cycle_(TCACycle) <i>Bacteroides uniformis</i>	-0.0123036	0.00459165	Propanoate_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	-0.0218885	-0.0670602
Gltate_cycle_(TCACycle) <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	-0.0365719	-0.0724681	Propanoate_metabolism <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	-0.0213239	-0.0245049
Gltate_cycle_(TCACycle) <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	-0.0473634	-0.0979925	Propanoate_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	-0.002103	-0.0306922
Gltate_cycle_(TCACycle) <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	-0.0393426	-0.0976341	Propanoate_metabolism <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	0.0118883	0.02073714
Gltate_cycle_(TCACycle) <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	0.18700343	0.1352342	Pyruvate_metabolism <i>Bacteroides uniformis</i>	-0.0422803	-0.0921327
Gltate_cycle_(TCACycle) <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	-0.0329655	-0.0110352	Pyruvate_metabolism <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	-0.0364955	-0.0702486
Gltate_cycle_(TCACycle) <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	-0.0384286	-0.0482036	Pyruvate_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	0.15290735	0.00404538
Cysteine_methionine_metabolism <i>Bacteroides uniformis</i>	-0.0534738	-0.1084937	Pyruvate_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	-0.0224948	-0.1010304
Cysteine_methionine_metabolism <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	-0.0391171	-0.0734806	Pyruvate_metabolism <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	-0.0518731	-0.1182136
Cysteine_methionine_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	0.02683465	-0.0895375	Pyruvate_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	0.03191536	0.08941692
Cysteine_methionine_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	-0.0732872	-0.1672791	Pyruvate_metabolism <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	-0.0313049	0.01081402
Cysteine_methionine_metabolism <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	0.16930047	-0.011449	Secondary_bile_acid_biosynthesis <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	-0.070859	-0.1899872
Cysteine_methionine_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	-0.0574743	-0.0478324	Sphingolipid_metabolism <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	-0.0707435	-0.1558627
Cysteine_methionine_metabolism <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	-0.0459755	-0.0823733	Sphingolipid_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	-0.0480328	-0.1020751
Fatty_acid_biosynthesis <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	-0.054355	-0.1331028	Sphingolipid_metabolism <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	0.00302496	0.0026892
Fatty_acid_biosynthesis <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	0.01180928	0.0446595	Sphingolipid_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	0.07224378	-0.0687131
Fatty_acid_biosynthesis <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	0.13161996	0.01468158	Starch_sucrose_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	0.10931292	0.02872667
Fatty_acid_biosynthesis <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	0.17142328	0.0956307	Starch_sucrose_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	0.05843321	-0.0578493
Fatty_acid_degradation <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	-0.0333133	-0.0450722	Starch_sucrose_metabolism <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	0.04243033	-0.0692128
Fatty_acid_degradation <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	-0.0518408	-0.1097163	Starch_sucrose_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	0.12795212	-0.0511098
Fatty_acid_degradation <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	0.0090592	0.01122093	Starch_sucrose_metabolism <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	-0.0032485	-0.0397679
Fructose_mannose_metabolism <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	0.02085311	0.06321989	Synthesis and degradation of ketone bodies <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	-0.0397837	-0.1345995
Fructose_mannose_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	0.07990683	0.1569279	Tryptophan_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	0.05427486	0.12993408
Fructose_mannose_metabolism <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	-0.0370269	-0.0419938	Tryptophan_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	-0.0432389	-0.1350475
Fructose_mannose_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	-0.0282621	-0.0004705	Tyrosine_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	-0.0647138	-0.1234953
Fructose_mannose_metabolism <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	-0.036474	-0.0801744	Valyne_leucine_isoleucine_biosynthesis <i>Bacteroides uniformis</i>	-0.0369219	-0.0414568
Galactose_metabolism <i>Bacteroides uniformis</i>	-0.047041	-0.0751224	Valyne_leucine_isoleucine_biosynthesis <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	-0.0172274	-0.0506811
Galactose_metabolism <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	0.03692171	0.10931652	Valyne_leucine_isoleucine_biosynthesis <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	-0.0191291	-0.0752678
Galactose_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	0.00647719	0.00436452	Valyne_leucine_isoleucine_biosynthesis <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	0.12890713	-0.0390076
Galactose_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	0.0383331	-0.1000509	Valyne_leucine_isoleucine_biosynthesis <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	0.02421914	-0.0658155
Galactose_metabolism <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	0.0263877	0.0431515	Valyne_leucine_isoleucine_biosynthesis <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	-0.0273044	-0.070694
Galactose_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	0.0927956	0.07512299	Valyne_leucine_isoleucine_biosynthesis <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	0.0281565	-0.0877008
Galactose_metabolism <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	0.01570023	-0.1021153	Valyne_leucine_isoleucine_degradation <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	-0.053973	-0.1627613
Glycerolipid_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	-0.0480968	-0.1046292	Valyne_leucine_isoleucine_degradation <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	-0.0543576	-0.1103114
Glycerolipid_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	-0.0410826	-0.0778977	Valyne_leucine_isoleucine_degradation <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	-0.0004455	-0.1226968
Glycerolipid_metabolism <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	-0.0512837	-0.1034357	UDCA	0.0318571	0.18728833
Glycerolipid_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	-0.0179159	-0.0428639	HDCA	0.12381823	0.22497026
Glycerolipid_metabolism <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	-0.074291	-0.1840143	GCA	0.26273764	0.16915474
Glycerophospholipid_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	0.00107726	0.01120388	CA	0.09803688	0.17612961
Glycerophospholipid_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	-0.0322393	-0.0694025	CDCA	0.09461606	0.166439
Glycerophospholipid_metabolism <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	0.02161453	-0.0434535	GDCA	0.63568879	0.01496889
Glycerophospholipid_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	0.17490803	0.01309418	DCA	0.07808028	0.23783547
Glycerophospholipid_metabolism <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	-0.0339757	-0.0988365	Free	0.13910779	0.16952039
Glycine_serine_threonine_metabolism <i>Bacteroides uniformis</i>	-0.0518845	-0.0806993	LCA	0.09889973	0.24130769
Glycine_serine_threonine_metabolism <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	-0.0321992	-0.0480549	Glyco	0.48128508	0.1079987
Glycine_serine_threonine_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	-0.0472385	-0.1053129	Primary	0.10273992	0.17421449
Glycine_serine_threonine_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	0.02529456	-0.069869	Secondary	0.09290263	0.2314309
Glycine_serine_threonine_metabolism <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	0.01854273	0.03127098	Total	0.10274423	0.24103386
Glycine_serine_threonine_metabolism <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	-0.0498555	-0.0392114	Cholesterol	-0.045817	0.26048194
Glycine_serine_threonine_metabolism <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	0.15703109	-0.0227147	Coprostanol	0.04587252	-0.057621
Glycolysis/gluconeogenesis <i>Bacteroides uniformis</i>	0.09945992	-0.0004881	Cholesterolan	-0.0064043	-0.1737653
Glycolysis/gluconeogenesis <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	-0.0354176	-0.0764224	Sitosterol	-0.0015629	0.17930497
Glycolysis/gluconeogenesis <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	0.09829039	-0.017426	5 α -sitosterol	0.02353579	-0.1898743
Glycolysis/gluconeogenesis <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	0.04242188	-0.0863507	5 β -sitosterol	0.09345976	-0.1293214
Glycolysis/gluconeogenesis <i>Collinsella aerofaciens</i>	0.03319151	0.10454868	Campesterol	-0.034006	0.18740311
Glycolysis/gluconeogenesis <i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	0.00479905	-0.0763129	5 α -campestanol	-0.035378	-0.1025233
Glycolysis/gluconeogenesis <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	0.11917693	-0.030391	Acetate	0.06144568	-0.1049988
Glycolysis/gluconeogenesis <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i>	0.12179793	-0.0486031	Propionate	0.23021587	0.289142
Glyoxylate_dicarboxylate_metabolism <i>Bacteroides uniformis</i>	-0.0639396	0.0942333	Butyrate	0.0282396	0.2494989
Glyoxylate_dicarboxylate_metabolism <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	-0.0259098	-0.0637778	iso-butyrate	0.12100257	0.24159476
Glyoxylate_dicarboxylate_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	0.12345606	-0.036593			
Glyoxylate_dicarboxylate_metabolism <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	-0.0561564	-0.1537441			

Table S5. Summary of the main distinctive features of the four microbiota clusters in terms of clinical, dietary and lipidomic profiles. BITE, Bulimic Investigatory Test Edinburgh; NDT, non-distinctive tracts; SCFAs, short-chain fatty acids.

	microbiota profile			
	C1	C2	C3	C4
clinical characteristics	NDT	↑ uric acid, BITE severity score	NDT	↑ BITE symptoms score ↓ uric acid
diet	↑ fiber intake	↑ energy intake ↓ fiber, fat intake	NDT	↑ energy, carbohydrate intake ↓ fat intake
lipidomics	↑ SCFAs	↑ SCFAs, cholesterol, bile acids	↑ converted sterols ↓ SCFAs	↑ bile acids ↓ SCFAs